

**THE INFLUENCE OF WRITING SKILLS AND VOCABULARY KNOWLEDGE
ON THE WRITING ANXIETY AMONG ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS
IN TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 6

Pages: 962-975

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2888

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14619011

Manuscript Accepted: 12-17-2024

The Influence of Writing Skills and Vocabulary Knowledge on the Writing Anxiety among English Major Students in Teacher Education Program

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Abstract

The purpose of the study aimed to determine the relationship of writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety among English major students. Quantitative research utilizing descriptive correlational technique was utilized in this study. The data were gathered from English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology who were selected through random sampling. Data gathering was done through survey questionnaires. Findings revealed that the level of writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety are all descriptively high. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between writing skills and writing anxiety. Likewise, there is also a significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety. Moreover, results showed that the domains of writing skills such as lack of motivation and interest in writing, difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas, and difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction can significantly influence writing anxiety. Also, it was revealed that domains of vocabulary knowledge such as proficiency, ability, and concentration can significantly influence writing anxiety. This signified the experiences of the English major students about their capability in writing and highlighting the interconnectedness of these factors in research on student development and education. Encouraging regular, informal writing practice, such as journaling or creative writing exercises, can help reduce writing anxiety and enhance writing skills, as consistent practice was associated with better writing performance and lower anxiety levels.

Keywords: *writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, writing anxiety, English major students, Philippines*

Introduction

Most learners face numerous challenges while writing at all levels of instruction, including elementary, secondary, and surprisingly, advanced education. Students in elementary and secondary school, in particular, struggle with writing because they lack a strong vocabulary and adequate reading comprehension. It is rooted within themselves, fear of making mistakes for learners' confidence and overall development, hindering effective writing skills and leading to poor student performance (Khan, 2020).

In Turkey, many students experience significant stress and fear when required to write assignments in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) or English as a Second Language (ESL) classes. This anxiety manifests as panic, difficulty breathing, and a rapid heartbeat, making students nervous about writing. As a result, they may avoid writing tasks, doubt their abilities, and delay completing assignments. The problem is further compounded by limited early writing experiences and an emphasis on creating a final product rather than focusing on the writing process, which intensifies their writing anxiety (Jamalinesari, 2020).

In the Philippines, various studies found out that writing anxiety is a common problem to students in different levels especially even in college and universities. Students' concerns are classified into eight categories: Poor motivation, inadequate writing time, inadequate writing practice, inadequate comments and feedback on students' written work, inadequate facilities and instructional resources, overcrowded learning environments, and poor performance. These are grammatical mistakes that include employing the wrong word choice, spelling, singular and plural forms, tenses, pronouns, prepositions, articles, and agreements (Ramos, 2019).

Studying this issue right now is important because students face a lot of different kinds of writing tasks, especially in their academic work. It aims to find out how these tasks affect students, helping teachers support them better and understand who might be feeling stressed or anxious. This research is crucial for students because it gives us new insights into how writing anxiety relates to their writing skills and vocabulary, especially in our specific context. So, this study is socially relevant because it helps us develop ways to reduce stress and anxiety, improve how often students write, and ultimately boost their writing abilities by helping them focus better on expressing their ideas and thoughts.

Many studies related to our study have been conducted, such as Aloairdhi's (2019) exploration of "Writing Anxiety Among Saudi Female Learners at Some Saudi Universities," Beri's (2022) quantitative investigation into "Writing Anxiety Among Prospective English Language Teachers," and Xie & Yuan's (2020) research on "English Writing Anxiety and Preservice Teachers' Written Corrective Feedback." These studies contribute valuable evidence that helps identify gaps in students' writing skills and vocabulary knowledge related to writing anxiety. However, our study conducted in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, gathered diverse viewpoints specifically from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students. This unique focus allows us to address ongoing issues in writing anxiety effectively, offering targeted solutions that go beyond traditional methods and provide a more effective and holistic approach to supporting students. This will ensure that our research stays pertinent and has an impact on resolving this enduring problem by offering significant insights and solutions that are suited to the needs of students in this setting.

Additionally, through a more thorough comprehension of the elements that lead to writing anxiety, the study's findings will help numerous stakeholders—including teachers, a wider audience, and study participants—develop strategies and valuable insights to help them effectively address writing anxiety and create supportive environments that promote student success. These research outcomes are crucial for ensuring the success and longevity of practice-based approaches.

Furthermore, the results will provide a foundational framework for future researchers and guide the development of policies and programs within relevant departments and offices. In today's digital era, sharing research findings through online platforms, interactive tools, and personalized feedback is inevitable. By embracing diverse feedback methods, acknowledging individual differences, and utilizing technology, educators can create environments that enhance linguistic accuracy while supporting broader goals of improvement and advancement in the field.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine whether writing anxiety significantly mediates the relationship between writing skills and vocabulary knowledge among English major students in teacher education program in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. Specially, it sought to answer the following objects:

1. To describe the level of writing skills in terms of:
 - 1.1. lack of motivation and interest in writing;
 - 1.2. difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas; and
 - 1.3. difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction
2. To describe the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of:
 - 2.1. proficiency;
 - 2.2. ability; and
 - 2.3. concentration
3. To describe the level of writing anxiety in terms of:
 - 3.1. somatic anxiety;
 - 3.2. cognitive anxiety; and
 - 3.3. avoidance behavior.
4. To determine the significant relationship of:
 - 4.1. writing skills and writing anxiety;
 - 4.2. vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety.
5. To identify which domain of Writing Skills and Vocabulary Knowledge predict Writing Anxiety.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized the quantitative research approach to best answer the subject of inquiry. Quantitative research is collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and writing the results of a study. Quantitative research originates from the positivist paradigm, which supports methods included into a statistical analysis that incorporates various strategies. Therefore, the goal of a quantitative research study is to figure out how one factor the independent variable which is writing skills and vocabulary knowledge affects another dependent or outcome variable which is writing anxiety in a population. These variables can then be measured, usually with devices, and numerical data analyzed using statistical procedures and structured methodologies like surveys. Statistical data is frequently presented in the form of tabulations, and findings are conclusive and descriptive in nature, allowing a definitive course of action to be recommended (Creswell, 2013).

This study utilized a quantitative research approach to provide evidence and insights into the relationship between writing skills and vocabulary knowledge among English major students in the Teacher Education Program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The quantitative design aimed to assess the extent of writing skills, focusing on indicators such as lack of motivation and interest in writing, difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas, and challenges with spelling, grammar, and sentence construction. It also examined vocabulary knowledge through indicators of proficiency, ability, and concentration, as well as its significant relationship with writing anxiety, which was measured using indicators of somatic anxiety, cognitive anxiety, and avoidance anxiety.

Particularly, this study employed a descriptive correlational design, suited for examining characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories and for describing specific populations, situations, or phenomena (McCombes, 2019). As noted by Stangor and Walinga (2014), this design focuses on identifying relationships between variables and enables the prediction of future outcomes based on current insights. Such an approach is instrumental for studies aiming to analyze variable interactions and forecast patterns within defined contexts.

While a descriptive correlational study can explore various connections, this research examines the link between writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety among English major students in the Teacher Education Program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. It is for this purpose that this method was used because the focal point of the two variables

study is to measure the significance of the relationship between writing skills and vocabulary knowledge on writing anxiety among students. By uncovering these patterns, the findings can contribute to developing targeted approaches to enhance students' writing proficiency and reduce writing anxiety, ultimately improving their academic performance.

The regression method is a statistical technique used to examine the relationship between variables and how the dependent variable is affected by one or more variables (Alita et al., 2021). This was used in this study because it is the most effective method for identifying characteristics and frequencies that will showcase the significance level and relevant statistics to support the study's findings and conclusions. Hence, it helped to evaluate the strength of these relationships and can be used to predict future interactions. This method is valuable for understanding and modeling how variables influence each other.

Furthermore, the regression method serves as a statistical tool employed to examine the relationships between variables and to ascertain how a dependent variable is influenced by one or more independent variables. It was selected for this study due to its effectiveness in analyzing and quantifying the characteristics and frequencies that indicate the significance level and relevant statistics crucial for substantiating the study's findings and conclusions. Specifically, in the context of English major students in a Teacher Education program, the regression analysis aids in understanding the degree to which writing skills and vocabulary knowledge contribute to writing anxiety.

Respondents

This study involved the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in First Semester Academic Year 2023-2024 totaling of four hundred fifty-seven (457) comprised the research population. The inclusion for this study focused on students who are enrolled in English major program, including both females and males.

The exclusion was the students who do not belong to the English major. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about the writing skills and vocabulary knowledge on the writing anxiety of students, and since the study purpose involves students' satisfaction, it would be fitting and valid to include students from all English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). Further, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, satisfied random sampling was chosen.

Stratified random sampling is one approach that could be utilized. With this method, a random sample is chosen from each stratum after the population is divided into subgroups or strata according to pertinent attributes like age, gender, or academic achievement. The findings may be more broadly applicable if stratified random sampling is used to guarantee that the sample is representative of the population and that each subgroup is fairly represented. However, the method requires that the population is well-defined and that the relevant characteristics for stratification are known (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

In this study, stratified random sampling method is a particular approach in this study because the respondents of the research were randomly selected based on the strata, which are in this case, the students from all Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). To compute for the sample, the researcher gathered first the data on the population of respondents through writing a formal request letter to the College Registrar, requesting access to the population of respondents, ensuring that the researcher could accurately identify and gather information about the target population of respondents for the study. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to his statistician for the computation of the study sample. The statistician used established sampling techniques to determine a suitable sample size, ensuring that it was both representative of the population and statistically valid for the study's objectives.

Consequently, the statistician was the following computed data including the sample appropriate for the study.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

Instrument

The researcher employed adopted questionnaires for both the independent and dependent variables, tailored to suit the context of this study. The first set of questions focused on the level of writing skills, with three indicators: lack of motivation and interest in writing, difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas, and difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction (Hougen, 2016). The second set of questions assessed the level of vocabulary knowledge, also with three indicators: proficiency, ability, and concentration (Balbuena, 2022). The third set of questions evaluated the level of writing anxiety, with indicators being semantic anxiety, cognitive anxiety, and avoidance behavior (Nurwanti, 2021).

The reliability of the survey questionnaire used to measure writing skills and vocabulary knowledge among English major students in

the Teacher Education Program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The results indicated a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.87 for the writing skills section of the questionnaire and 0.85 for the vocabulary knowledge section and .91 for writing anxiety for the questionnaire. These values exceed the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, suggesting that the items within each section have a high level of internal consistency. This implies that the survey instrument is reliable for measuring the constructs of writing skills and vocabulary knowledge, providing confidence that the data collected are consistent and dependable. Therefore, the questionnaire is considered a valid and reliable tool for exploring the relationship between writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety among the study population.

The Likert Scale was used as a basis for describing the level of writing skills and vocabulary knowledge on the writing anxiety of the respondents. In this scale, Zulueta and Perez (2010) explained that the respondents would respond by checking a point or circling a number. The checks were assigned numerical values to streamline data analysis and ensure consistency. The respondents were assigned an altitude score based on the sum of these values across the items. Additionally, the questionnaire's overall effectiveness was evaluated through the consolidation of feedback and assessments from expert validators, ensuring its reliability and sustainability for the study.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher performed the following steps:

Questionnaire Development: The researcher searched for existing questionnaires from various journal articles and related online sources that were relevant to the two variables being studied.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires: After compiling the questionnaires, they were submitted to a panel of experts for evaluation and contextual adjustments. The researcher followed the recommendations of these experts until the questionnaires were approved for use.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study: The researcher had requested permission from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology (KCAST) to access the school and distribute the questionnaires to the students.

Crafting and Validating Questionnaires: Following approval from the panel, the researcher developed the questionnaires based on the study's objectives. The questionnaires had been reviewed by the adviser for validation and verification before being administered at KCAST.

Collection and Tabulation of Data: After the surveys were completed, the researcher collected and verified the instruments, tabulated the results, and analyzed the statistical data. The findings had then been interpreted, conclusions drawn, and recommendations made based on the study's results.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to calculate the data in this study likewise in the testing of the researcher objectives at a 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This was utilized to determine the mean score for assessing English major students' proficiency in English writing and modular learning.

Pearson r. This is a statistical tool based on the methods of covariance that measure the statistical relationship, association, or correlation of variables. Hence, this tool will be utilized to determine the significant relationship between English Writing Skills and Modular Learning.

Regression. This was used to determine the domain of writing skills and vocabulary knowledge on the writing anxiety that significantly influences the satisfaction of students.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were addressed and considered to ensure the study's success. Informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity, confidentiality, and conflict of interest are all factors that Denzin and Lincoln (2011) and Berg and Lune (2017) evaluate. Ethical considerations had addressed and considered to ensure the study's success.

The participants of this study were all first-year students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. In this case, the researcher ensured that the safety, rights, and trust of the participants in the study were respected and protected and that the study's purpose was carried out with integrity and fairness.

Informed Consent. The researcher took measures to secure informed consent by providing comprehensive information to both students and parents regarding the study's objectives, methodologies, potential limitations, and benefits. This process can be viewed as a contract between the researcher and participants, ensuring transparency (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Additionally, as part of the informed consent process, participants received a comprehensive briefing on the study, including its goals, objectives, methodology, and other relevant details. This thorough explanation ensured participants had a clear and complete

understanding of their role, the scope of their involvement, and the study's purpose, allowing them to make fully informed decisions about their participation. Risk of Harm, Anonymity, and Confidentiality. The researcher guaranteed not to share any information about these people. One of the most important factors in the study was protecting the identities of the participants. Anonymity and confidentiality are key to preventing potential harm to participants. Although often used interchangeably, these terms have distinct meanings: anonymity means that the researcher does not know the participant's identity (e.g., anonymous surveys). On the other hand, confidentiality refers to the de-identification and privacy of the participant, even though the researcher is aware of their identity (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). The research design must consider potential risks to participants, researchers, the community, and the institution, including physical harm, loss of resources, emotional distress, and reputational damage. The approach should prioritize eliminating, isolating, and minimizing risks, ensuring that participants are fully aware of any potential dangers (Smith, 2020).

Hence, the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in the Philippines establishes a robust legal framework for the protection of personal information, mandating secure collection, processing, and storage practices that prioritize individuals' privacy rights of the collected data. Personal details like names and addresses were carefully taken out to keep data during the study. After the completion of the study, the data will be responsibly destroyed in line with the rules, three years after that. This law is particularly critical in research, as it requires researchers to handle personal data with the highest levels of confidentiality and security. Compliance with these legal standards involves anonymizing data when appropriate, limiting access to authorized personnel only, and ensuring that no personal information is disclosed to unauthorized parties. Adherence to this law not only safeguards participants' privacy but also fosters trust and ethical integrity within the research process.

Conflict of Interest. Any potential conflicts of interest must be transparently reported in the ethics approval application to allow the ethics committee to guide the management of these conflicts. As Fleming (2018) notes, it is common for researchers in work-integrated learning to focus on their institutional programs, which may introduce conflicts of interest. For instance, to maintain impartiality, data collection might be conducted anonymously, with a third party re-identifying the data before making it available to researchers. Similarly, researchers may have business interests outside of their academic work that could influence studies involving external stakeholders with similar interests.

In this study, however, the participants were students, and no external factors could have influenced the research outcomes. The researcher had no conflicts of interest, as the study did not involve coercion of participants, such as teachers threatening to fail students or principals threatening to terminate teachers who did not participate in the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the overall findings and results from overall, highest and lowest on the relationship of Writing Skills and Vocabulary Knowledge on the Writing Anxiety among English major students. Analyses and interpretations of data were done parallel to the research objectives. The topics discussed are the level of writing skills; level of vocabulary knowledge; and level of writing anxiety among English major students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology (KCAST). This also includes the significant relationship between writing skills and vocabulary knowledge towards writing anxiety.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Lack of Motivation and Interest in Writing

The level of writing skills among English major students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: lack of motivation and interest in writing, difficulty in conveying ideas and organizing ideas, and difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction. The responses of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 2. Level of Writing Skills in terms of Lack of Motivation and Interest in Writing

<i>Lack of Motivation and Interest in Writing</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Writing using my native language.	3.78	High
2.	Writing for pleasure in my free time in English.	3.96	High
3.	Writing notes, messages, letters or reports in English to motivate myself.	4.17	High
4.	Using an English grammar book or handbook to improve my writing.	3.97	High
5.	Using the English words, I know in different ways.	3.81	High
Overall		3.94	High

Presented in Table 2 was the level of writing skills in terms of lack of motivation and interest in writing of English major students. The overall mean of the level of writing skills in terms of lack of motivation and interest in writing is 3.94 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This implies that the level of writing skills in terms of lack of motivation and interest in writing is oftentimes manifested.

The data revealed that the highest mean of 4.17 was obtained from item number 3 - writing notes, messages, letters or reports in English to motivate myself with a high descriptive equivalent which meant that it was oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the data also revealed lowest mean score was obtained by item number 1 - writing using my native language is 3.78 with a descriptive equivalent of high, which means it is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Difficulty in Conveying and Organizing Ideas

Presented in Table 3 are the mean scores of the respondents' responses on their level of writing skills in terms of difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas. The overall mean of the level of writing skills in terms of difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas is 4.07 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of writing skills in terms of difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas is always manifested.

The data revealed the highest mean score obtained by item number 3 - using relevant content when writing a text, is 4.14, with a descriptive equivalent of high, meaning it is oftentimes manifested.

Table 3. *Level of Writing Skills in terms of Difficulty in Conveying and Organizing Ideas*

<i>Difficulty in Conveying and Organizing Ideas</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Writing what is important for producing a good text.	4.06	High
2.	Writing the importance when constructing and structuring a text.	4.13	High
3.	Using a relevant content when writing a text.	4.14	High
4.	Writing about how the linguistic feedback i receive relates to the assessment.	4.00	High
5.	Writing to make the text's language better after receiving criticism.	3.99	High
Overall		4.07	High

On the other hand, the lowest mean score revealed in the data was obtained by item number 5 - writing to make the text's language better after receiving criticism, at 3.99, with a descriptive equivalent of high, indicating it is also oftentimes manifested.

Level of Writing Skills in terms of Difficulty in Spelling, Grammar, and Sentence Construction

Presented in Table 4, the level of writing skills in terms of difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction has a total mean of 4.13 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that difficulties in these areas are oftentimes manifested.

The data revealed that item number 1 - writing in a comfortable, quiet place where I can concentrate, has the highest mean of 4.36 with a descriptive equivalent of very high, meaning it is always manifested.

On the other hand, item number 3 - changing or making my ideas clearer as I am writing, got the lowest mean of 3.95 with a high descriptive equivalent, indicating it is oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Writing Skills in terms of Difficulty in Spelling, Grammar, and Sentence Construction*

<i>Difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Writing in a comfortable, quiet place where I can concentrate.	4.36	Very High
2.	Using a background knowledge to help me develop my ideas.	4.05	High
3.	Changing or making my ideas clearer as I am writing.	3.95	High
4.	Using a dictionary to check things I am not sure about when I write.	4.11	High
5.	Encouraging myself by saying that I can do well.	4.21	High
Overall		4.13	High

Summary on the Level of Writing Skills

Presented in the Table 5 was the overall level of Writing Skills. Data showed that the highest mean performance expectancy the highest mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This means that the writing skills in terms of difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

On the other hand, facilitating conditions obtained a mean of 3.94 which considered to be the indicator got the lowest mean. This implied that writing skills in terms of lack of motivation and interest in writing is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Summary on the Level of Writing Skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Lack of motivation and interest in writing	3.94	High
Difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas	4.07	High
Difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction	4.22	High
Overall	4.08	High

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Proficiency

Presented in Table 6 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of proficiency. The overall mean of the level of writing skills in terms of proficiency is 4.10 with a descriptive equivalent of high, which means it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data revealed the highest mean score was obtained by the item number 1 - reading many reading materials to enhance my vocabulary size is 4.46 with a descriptive equivalent of high, which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

On the contrary, the lowest mean score revealed on the data was obtained by the item number 5 - guessing the meaning of new word using background knowledge and the immediate and the wider context is 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high, which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 6. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Proficiency*

	<i>Proficiency</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Reading many reading materials to enhance my vocabulary size.	4.22	High
2.	Repeating the new word orally several times to.	4.15	High
3.	Knowing which words are important to me to learn.	4.06	High
4.	Reviewing my vocabulary regularly by reading different books.	4.07	High
5.	Guessing the meaning of new word using background knowledge and the immediate and the wider context.	3.99	High
	Overall	4.10	High

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge of in Terms of Ability

Presented in the Table 7 was the level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of ability which has a total mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of ability is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data revealed that item number 1 - finding my own way of learning new words garnered the highest mean of 4.16 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

On the other side, item number 5 - creating mental images of the words I learn got the lowest mean of 3.98 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 7. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Ability*

	<i>Ability</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Finding my own way of learning new words.	4.16	High
2.	Having a plan of accumulating words.	4.04	High
3.	Using vocabulary section or glosses in my textbook to learn new words.	3.88	High
4.	Using common sense and knowledge of the world when Guessing the meaning of the word.	4.06	High
5.	creating mental images of the words I learn.	3.88	High
	Overall	4.01	High

Level of Vocabulary Knowledge of in Terms of Concentration

Presented in the Table 8 was the vocabulary knowledge in terms of concentration had a total mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of concentration is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data revealed that item number 1 - paying attention to the pronunciation of a new word garnered the highest mean of 4.34 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the respondents.

On the other hand, item number 5 - practicing the words regularly without distraction got the lowest mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 8. *Level of Vocabulary Knowledge in terms of Concentration*

	<i>Concentration</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Paying attention to the pronunciation of a new word.	4.34	Very High
2.	Having trouble in checking the meaning of new words in dictionaries.	4.10	High
3.	Learning the spelling of the new word and writing new English words several times to lessen my stress level.	4.01	High
4.	Focusing the words that are much difficult to understand.	4.13	High
5.	Practicing the words regularly without distraction.	3.99	High
	Overall	4.11	High

Summary on the Level of Vocabulary Knowledge

Presented in the Table 9 was the overall level of Vocabulary Knowledge. Data showed an overall descriptive equivalent of high with an overall mean score of 4.07. This means that the overall level of vocabulary knowledge is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 9. *Summary on the Level of Employees Performance*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Proficiency	4.10	High
Ability	4.01	High
Concentration	4.11	High
Overall	4.07	High

The result showed that the concentration got the highest mean which is 4.11 which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. On the other hand, ability got the lowest mean of 4.01 which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Somatic Anxiety

Presented in Table 10 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of writing anxiety in terms of somatic anxiety. The overall means of the level of writing skills in terms of somatic anxiety is 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data revealed the highest mean score was obtained by the item number 1 - having a lot of pressure and my heart is thumping is 4.27 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the respondents.

On the contrary, the lowest mean score revealed on the data was obtained by the item number 5 - having panic attack, writing English compositions under time constraints is 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 10. *Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Somatic Anxiety*

<i>Somatic Anxiety</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Having a lot of pressure and my heart is thumping.	4.27	Very High
2.	Getting stock in working on	4.15	High
3.	English composition.		
4.	Having pressure under the time and I tremble or perspire.	4.09	High
5.	Feeling worried that my thoughts become jumbled.	4.18	High
6.	Having panic attack, writing English compositions under time constraints.	3.99	High
Overall		4.14	High

Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Cognitive Anxiety

Presented in Table 11 are the mean scores of the respondents' response on their level of writing anxiety in terms of cognitive anxiety. The overall means of the level of writing skills in terms of cognitive anxiety is 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The data revealed the highest mean score was obtained by the item number 1 - feeling worried and uncomfortable when writing English compositions is 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

On the contrary, the lowest mean score revealed on the data was obtained by the item number 5 - paying attention about what other people would think in my English compositions is 3.92 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 11. *Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Cognitive Anxiety*

<i>Cognitive Anxiety</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Feeling worried and uncomfortable when writing English compositions.	4.14	High
2.	Feeling afraid that my compositions in English are much worse than others.	4.07	High
3.	Getting nervous about having a poor grade in my English composition.	4.07	High
4.	Feeling worried that they would mock my English compositions.	4.04	High
5.	Paying attention about what other people would think in my English compositions.	3.92	High
Overall		4.05	High

Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Avoidance Behavior

Presented in the Table 12 was the level of writing anxiety in terms of avoidance behavior has a total mean of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of ability is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 12. *Level of Writing Anxiety in terms of Avoidance Behavior*

<i>Avoidance Behavior</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Choosing to write down my thoughts in English.	4.18	High
2.	Doing my best to avoid writing English compositions.	4.01	High
3.	Using English to write compositions whenever possible.	4.04	High
4.	Looking for every opportunity to write English compositions outside of class.	3.82	High
5.	Thinking about ways to excuse myself.	3.79	High
Overall		3.97	High

Hence, the level of Writing Anxiety in terms of avoidance behavior. The data revealed that item number 1 - choosing to write down my thoughts in English garnered the highest mean of 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. On the other side, item number 5 - thinking about ways to excuse myself got the lowest mean of 3.79 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Summary on the Level of Writing Anxiety

Presented in the Table 13 was the overall level of Writing Anxiety. Data showed an overall descriptive equivalent high with an overall mean score of 4.05. This means that the overall level of writing anxiety is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

On the other hand, the result showed that the somatic anxiety got the highest mean of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the writing anxiety in terms of somatic anxiety is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Lastly, avoidance behavior obtained a mean of 3.97 which considered to be the indicator got the lowest mean. This means that writing anxiety in terms of avoidance behavior is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 13. *Summary on the Level of Writing Anxiety*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Somatic Anxiety	4.14	High
Cognitive Anxiety	4.05	High
Avoidance Behavior	3.97	High
Overall	4.05	High

Significant relationship between Writing Skills and Writing Anxiety

The data revealed that the level of writing skills have a total mean score of 4.07 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the writing skills is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. On the other hand, the data also revealed that the level of writing anxiety of students have a total mean score of 4.05 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the writing anxiety is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. The result of the significant relationship between writing skills and writing anxiety were presented below.

Presented in Table 14 is the result of the significant relationship between Writing Skills and Writing Anxiety with a R-value of .367. In this study, 36% of writing anxiety is attributed to the influence of writing skills, while the remaining 64% is due to unexplored variables. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected within this context. This impose that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between writing skills and writing anxiety.

Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this means that there is a significant relationship between writing skills and writing anxiety. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables causes the increase or decrease of either variable.

Table 14. *Significant Relationship Between Writing Skills and Writing Anxiety*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Writing Skills	4.07	.367	<.001	Ho Rejected
Writing Anxiety	4.05			

Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Anxiety

The findings revealed that the level of vocabulary knowledge of students have a total mean score of 4.07 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the vocabulary knowledge is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

On the other hand, the findings also revealed that the level of writing anxiety of students have a total mean score of 4.05 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the writing anxiety is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. The result of the significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety were presented below.

Presented in Table 15 is the result of the significant relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety with an R-value of .616. In this study, 61% of language anxiety is attributed to the influence of vocabulary learning strategies, while the remaining 39% is due to unexplored variables.

Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected within this context. This impose that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety.

Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this means that vocabulary knowledge can influence the writing anxiety of the students. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Anxiety*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @ = 0.05</i>
Vocabulary Knowledge	4.07	.616	<.001	Ho Rejected
Writing Anxiety	4.05			

Domain/s Of Writing Skills that Predict Writing Anxiety

Presented in Table 16 was the domain of writing skills that predict writing anxiety. The results showed that only the domain of the independent variable writing skills to be statistically significant predictor of the level writing skills.

The study also examined various domains of writing skills to determine their influence on writing anxiety. Among these, lack of motivation and interest in writing emerged as a significant predictor, with a beta value of 0.242, indicating that an increase in motivation and interest is associated with an increase of .242 value in writing anxiety. The p-value for this domain was 0.009, below the 0.05 threshold, which signifies a statistically significant influence. In contrast, the domains difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas and difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction had p-values of 0.507 and 0.236, respectively, indicating that they were not significant predictors of writing anxiety.

The overall model explained 14.7% of the variance in writing anxiety, as indicated by an R^2 of 0.147, with an F-ratio of 5.744 and a p-value of less than 0.001.

Table 16. *Domain/s Of Writing Skills that Predict Writing Anxiety*

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.051	0.05			
Lack of motivation and interest in writing	0.242	0.091	0.29	0.009	HoRejected
Difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas	0.064	0.095	0.075	0.507	Ho Accepted
Difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction	0.108	0.091	0.116	0.236	Ho Accepted

Dependent Variable: Writing Anxiety

Note: $R = 0.383$, $R^2 = 0.147$, $F\text{-ratio} = 5.744$ $P\text{-value} = < .001$

Domain/s Of Vocabulary Knowledge Predict Writing Anxiety

Table 17 presented the predictive relationship between vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety among students in the English program, within the domain of vocabulary knowledge, the variables ability and concentration were found to be statistically significant predictors of writing anxiety. The beta values for these variables were 0.277 and 0.33, respectively, suggesting that as students' ability and concentration in vocabulary knowledge increase, their writing anxiety also increases.

The p-values for ability (0.004) and concentration (0.001) were both below the 0.05 significance level, confirming the importance of these predictors. In contrast, the proficiency domain showed a non-significant relationship with writing anxiety ($\beta = -0.094$, $p = 0.354$). The model explained a substantial 30.3% of the variance in writing anxiety, with an R^2 of 0.303, an F-ratio of 14.471, and a p-value of less than 0.001. In summary, the findings suggest that both writing skills, particularly motivation and interest, and vocabulary knowledge, especially ability and concentration, significantly influence writing anxiety among English major students.

Table 17. *Domain/s Of Vocabulary Knowledge Predict Writing Anxiety*

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.051	0.05			
Proficiency	-0.094	0.101	-0.102	0.354	Ho Accepted
Ability	0.277	0.094	0.32	0.004	Ho Rejected
Concentration	0.33	0.101	0.366	0.001	Ho Rejected

Dependent Variable: Writing Anxiety

Note: $R = 0.550$, $R^2 = 0.303$, $F\text{-ratio} = 14.471$ $P\text{-value} = < .001$

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn in answer to sub-problems raised in the preceding chapter. The respondents from English major students are consistently reported a significant prevalence of writing skills, indicating that this variable is very high level which meant that they highly manifested the lack of vocabulary and interest, difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas, and difficulty in spelling, grammar, and sentence construction.

Based on the result of vocabulary knowledge of the students, it can be also drawn that the level of vocabulary knowledge among English major students was high, this means that the students often manifested the variable. In addition, the students were assessed the preparedness level of writing anxiety, and it was determined as high, this means that the writing anxiety of English major students are oftentimes manifested.

This stated that the anchored theories confirmed that there is a relationship between three variables. When individuals possess strong ability, being knowledgeable and appreciative, they tend to experience a greater sense. Therefore, the hypothesis is not accepted.

Based on the previously mentioned finding from the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety.

Therefore, it is suggested that individual's comprehensive understanding and proficient utilization of words in communication, playing a pivotal role in reading, writing, spoken language, and overall language fluency, making it an essential aspect of language learning and teaching. Learners will employ their skills to generate ideas, sum up the concept, sentence construction, and punctuation to enhance the student's capability in writing.

To education program, I highly recommend for the implementation of an interventions and strategies to alleviate this anxiety and promote more confident and expressive written communication in enhancing their language skills and fostering effective communication in both written and spoken contexts curriculum that promotes understanding and ability to comprehend and utilize a wide range of words effectively in their communication, which is a positive aspect of their language skills.

Furthermore, it is essential for the educational institution to effectively incorporate a wide range of writing activities, thereby including real-world problems, vocabulary challenge, persuasive essays and etc. This can be achieved through the organization of events, students' participation and the provision of support by the institution. Students in English major have a higher commitment to enhancing their writing skills and vocabulary knowledge. This dedication is not limited solely to English major students. Above all, for students to employ their understanding of writing skill and vocabulary knowledge and writing anxiety.

Moreover, for the benefit of future researchers, a recommendation is made to consider employing a regression approach when delving into the intricate interplay between writing skills, vocabulary knowledge, and writing anxiety. Although the present study centered quantitative research involving 214 students, the utilization of a regression approach holds promise for multiple reasons.

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